

COcyber AI Security DeepHack

The context

With phishing attacks becoming more sophisticated, leveraging AI for cybersecurity defence has become essential. Traditional rule-based detection methods are no longer sufficient. Instead, AI-driven solutions that understand phishing tactics, identify deception patterns, and adapt to new threats are necessary to protect individuals and organisations.

48	4	16	4
hours	teams	participants	countries

The vision

During the DeepHack, participants used natural language processing (NLP), anomaly detection, and existing phishing threat intelligence sources to develop AI-driven systems able to analyse linguistic anomalies, behavioural patterns, and suspicious URLs in emails and websites to detect, identify and prevent phishing attacks in real-time. The challenge required participants to focus on dual-use cybersecurity technologies to ensure that the final solutions could target both civilian and defence cybersecurity applications, while addressing practical deployment issues such as multilingual attacks, AI bias, infrastructure constraints, and adversarial threats.

The winners

The DeepHack was a technical sprint and a clear demonstration of how interdisciplinary and cross-cultural teams can build smart, resilient and ethical AI systems under pressure. In these 48 hours, participants went through dedicated checkpoints and mentoring to prepare a final pitch of their solution, and received well-deserved recognition for their hard work.

A shared challenge

From April 24 to 26, 2025, COcyber's AI Cybersecurity Deephack brought together cyber enthusiasts from academia, research and the start-up scene for an intense 48-hour challenge to answer one critical question: **can artificial intelligence stop the next big phishing attack?**

The goals

- Protect **civilian organisations** from cyber fraud and data breaches.
- Defend **military and defence entities** against nation-state cyber espionage and disruption.
- Strengthen **supply chain resilience**.
- Ensure **threat intelligence sharing** between sectors to counter emerging phishing tactics.

ALVAR

1st place

Fahad Sohrab, Heidi Mäenpää, Viktor Växby

ALVAR (Anomaly Learning and Verification for Attack Resilience) is an AI-driven system based on Multimodal Subspace Support Vector Data Description. The system is trained to learn from the "non-attack" samples across multiple data modalities, such as textual content, system commands and metadata. The robustness and scalability of ALVAR's model allows it to flag evolving and advanced AI powered threats.

Dual-use potential

ALVAR leverages Multimodal Subspace Support Vector Data Description (MSSVDD) to adapt to enable seamless protection of critical infrastructure and defense assets alike. Key features such as plug-and-play modules, flexible deployment options (cloud, edge and on-premises) and real-time anomaly verification provide strong resilience against evolving threats and ensure it can be deployed in both civilian and defence contexts alike.

MORPH

2nd place

Daniele Lunghi, Jérémie Bogaert, Khaled Rahal, Gian Marco Paldino

MORPH (Machine-learning for Observing Robust Phishing Hazards) employs federated learning to enable collaborative defense while keeping sensitive data private. The system incorporates adversarial robustness techniques to defend against sophisticated evasion tactics employed in modern phishing attempts. The solution features advanced intent classification that categorizes attacks into six distinct categories, helping organizations gather hints on the attacks that go beyond simple binary detection.

Dual-use potential

MORPH is designed to operate in both air-gapped military networks and cloud enterprise environments through a unified architecture, breaking down the traditional silos between military and civilian cybersecurity solutions. Its federated learning approach ensures that sensitive data remains protected, critical for defense operations and privacy-conscious enterprises.

PhishNet

3rd place

Vidura Ravihansai, Isuru Pinto, Rashmi Ratnayake, Chamara Sandeepa

PhishNet uses a combination of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to tackle phishing attacks. The GNN monitors the messaging flow between people in an organization to spot unusual communication patterns. If something looks suspicious, the LLM checks the message content more deeply, looking for specific wording or behaviours that might indicate phishing. PhishNet also relies on open phishing threat intelligence databases to check if any part of the message matches already known phishing sources.

Dual-use potential

For defence contexts, PhishNet's federated learning approach protects sensitive data during training, so models can learn without sharing private information across organizations. For civilian use, its LLM-based phishing detection works independently to analyse email content and detect phishing, across multiple languages. These flexible components make Phishnet able to adapt to different environments while keeping security and privacy in mind.

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